

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part V. Condensation of Cotarnine with Aromatic Nitro-aldehydes.

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Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 1458) condensed cotarnine with 6-nitropiperonal and stated that the product was undoubtedly 6-nitropiperonylhydrocotarnine and thus belonged to a new class of isoquinoline derivatives. In a later paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 840), however, they published a correction regarding the composition of this compound ; they observed that the results of analysis of the product agreed with the assumption that the reaction had occurred between 1 molecule of the base and 2 molecules of the nitro-aldehyde and assigned the following structure to the condensation product on the basis of the well known reactivity of the 5- or *ana*-position in cotarnine :—

This reaction has now been found to be a general one for aromatic nitro-aldehydes, 2 molecules of the nitro-aldehyde condensing with 1 molecule of the base with the elimination of 1 molecule of water. Further, the observation has been made that if position 5 in the cotarnine molecule be blocked by a substituent, *e.g.*, the bromine atom, reaction occurs with only 1 molecule of the nitro-aldehyde, thus affording confirmation of the assumption made by Robinson

regarding the point of attachment of the second molecule of the nitro-aldehyde. Attention may be drawn in this connection to the recent work of Ahluwalia, Kaul and Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 197) who describe a product (m. p. 154°) which is obviously identical with the compound prepared by us, by the condensation of cotarnine with *o*-nitro-benzaldehyde. Their assumption that the compound is *o*-nitro-benzaldehydo-1-hydrocotarnine seems, however, to be incorrect as the complete analysis of the base and its hydrochloride clearly point to its being derived from the condensation of 2 molecules of the aldehyde with 1 molecule of the base. The formula proposed by the above-mentioned workers appears to have been based on an estimation only of nitrogen in the compound, but as would be seen from a comparison of the percentage values of nitrogen for the two compounds, this determination is not sufficient to enable one to distinguish between the two formulæ.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-(o-Nitro) - benzaldehydo- 1 - (o-nitro) - benzoylhydrocotarnine.— Cotarnine (1 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.28 g.) in the proportion of 1 to 2 molecules were dissolved in absolute alcohol (12 c. c.) by warming to 50° on the water-bath and the clear solution exposed in a quartz flask to direct sunlight for 3-4 hours. The crystals of a cream colour which separated out were filtered, washed with a little alcohol and dried in the desiccator. The substance was quite pure and melted sharply at 153°, yield 0.8 g. The same product was also obtained in a diminished yield by keeping the mixture in the dark for 24 hours. It is very sparingly soluble in alcohol and in most of the common organic solvents. (Found: C, 60.16; H, 4.65. $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3$ requires C, 59.88; H, 4.41 per cent).

The sparingly soluble *hydrochloride* of the base was prepared by dissolving it in glacial acetic acid and adding a few drops of 4 *N*-hydrochloric acid; it separated almost immediately in the form of fine colourless crystals, m. p. 172° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 7.06. $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 6.4 per cent).

The *hydrobromide* of the base, prepared similarly, separated in the form of colourless plates, m. p. 177° (decomp.). [Found: Br, 12.98; H_2O (at 110°/5 mm.), 2.35. $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3 \cdot HBr \cdot H_2O$ requires Br, 12.8; H_2O 2.9 per cent]. The *nitrate* separated in the form of prisms, m. p. 181° (decomp.) on the addition of dilute nitric acid to

the glacial acetic acid solution of the base. The *sulphate*, prepared in the same manner, crystallised in clusters of prisms, m. p. 191-92° (decomp.). The *picrate* separated in short thin yellow needles, m. p. 175-76°.

5-(*o*-Amino)-benzaldehydo-1-(*o*-amino)-benzoylhydrocotarnine.—The well powdered nitro-compound (1 g.) was gradually added to a mixture of stannous chloride (3 g.), hydrochloric acid (5 c. c.) and a small piece of granulated tin and the whole shaken for a few hours. Water (50 c. c.) was added, the clear liquid was basified with excess of 25% sodium hydroxide, and the separated solid washed with water, dried on a porous plate and then in the desiccator and the dry solid, extracted with warm benzene (60°). The amino compound separated from the benzene solution as a pale yellow crystalline solid, m. p. 122°. On diazotising its solution in cold hydrochloric acid and coupling with β -naphthol, a deep red dyestuff was thrown down. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 5.88. $C_{26}H_{27}O_5N_3$ requires C, 67.68; H, 5.85 per cent). The *diacetyl* derivative of the amine separated from alcohol as a colourless crystalline powder, m.p. 126°.

5-(*m*-Nitro)-benzaldehydo-1-(*m*-nitro)-benzoylhydrocotarnine separated in a crystalline form on warming an alcoholic solution of cotarnine (1 mol.) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (2 mols.) to 60° for 1 hour and then leaving at room temperature for 2 days. The crystals, after washing with cold alcohol, were pure and melted at 146°. It was sparingly soluble in the common organic solvents. (Found: C, 60.17; H, 4.76. $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3$ requires C, 59.88; H, 4.41 per cent). It formed a sparingly soluble hydrochloride crystallising in plates, m.p. 188° (decomp.). (Found: Cl (HCl), 6.25. $C_{26}H_{23}O_9N_3 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 6.4 per cent).

5-(*m*-Amino)-benzaldehydo-1-(*m*-amino)-benzoylhydrocotarnine.—The nitro-compound was reduced and the product isolated in the same manner as the corresponding *ortho*-compound. The amine, m.p. 113°, dissolved easily in benzene and gave an azo-dye in the usual way.

5-(6-Nitro-3:4-dimethoxy)-benzaldehydo-1-(6-nitro-3:4-dimethoxy)-benzoylhydrocotarnine, prepared in the same way from cotarnine and nitrovanillin methyl ether, formed yellow crystals, m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 55.38; H, 4.94. $C_{30}H_{31}O_{13}N_3$ requires C, 56.1; H, 4.83 per cent). The *hydrochloride* of the base, m.p. 193° (decomp.) was sparingly soluble in water. [Found: Cl (HCl), 4.69. $C_{30}H_{31}O_{13}N_3 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 5.23 per cent].

1-(*o*-Nitro-)-benzoyl-5-bromohydrocotarnine.—A mixture of 5-bromocotarnine (1 g., 1 mol.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.9 g., 2 mols.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) was exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hours. The solution was then poured into water (50 c.c.), when an oil separated out which hardened to a gritty solid after 24 hours. It was purified by dissolving in cold acid and reprecipitating with caustic soda, and then crystallising from alcohol by dilution with water. It formed indefinite crystals, m.p. 120°, sintering a few degrees before this temperature. Repeated purification from alcohol, however, did not improve the m.p. (Found: N, 6.93. $C_{19}H_{17}O_6N_2Br$ requires N, 6.24 per cent).

The sparingly soluble *hydrobromide* of the base separated as crystals on adding a solution of hydrobromic acid to the base in glacial acetic acid, m.p. 162° (decomp.). [Found: Br (HBr), 15.33. $C_{19}H_{17}O_6N_2Br$, HBr requires Br (HBr), 15.09 per cent].

5-(6-Nitro)-piperonyl-1-(6-nitro) piperonyl hydrocotarnine (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1468).—Cotarnine (1 g.) and 6-nitropiperonal (1.64 g.) were dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.), slightly warmed on the water-bath and exposed to sunlight. A greenish yellow crystalline solid began to separate after an hour. The solid was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol as a yellow crystalline powder sparingly soluble in alcohol, m.p. 168°. The *hydrobromide* of the base, prepared as before, melted at 180° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 12.25. $C_{28}H_{23}O_{13}N_3$, HBr requires Br, 11.58 per cent).

1-(6-Nitro)-piperonyl-5-bromohydrocotarnine.—5-Bromocotarnine (1 g.) and 6-nitropiperonal (0.62 g.) were mixed with rectified spirit (15 c.c.), slightly warmed till a clear solution was obtained and left for 24 hours. The yellow crystalline solid was collected and washed with cold alcohol, in which it was almost insoluble, m.p. 125°. (Found: N, 5.95. $C_{20}H_{17}O_8NBr$ requires N, 5.68 per cent). The *hydrobromide* of the base melted at 172°. [Found: Br, 13.3. $C_{20}H_{17}O_8N_2Br$, HBr requires Br (HBr) 13.93 per cent].

On attempting the condensation of *o*-nitro-aldehydes with hydrocotarnine and narcotine in alcoholic medium in exactly the same way, only unchanged materials were recovered.